

Action of Electrolytes on Lyophobic Sols

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Dhar and coworkers showed that besides the valency of the oppositely charged ion of the electrolyte its precipitation value for a lyophobic sol is defined by the specific adsorption of similarly and oppositely charged ions by the colloid particles, dilution of the sol, and also on the mode of addition of electrolytes, in parts or all at once.

The precipitation value is affected by the time 't' the electrolyte is in contact with the sol. It is also affected by temperature. Ghosh and coworkers showed the applicability of the rate equation for a chemical reaction to coagulation process, so that $\frac{1}{t} = kpz \exp(-E/RT)$, where $\frac{1}{t}$ is proportional to the rate of coagulation, p is the probability of forma-

tion of a stable aggregate, E the energy of activation, and z is number of collisions in unit time. In this paper further experimental support has been obtained by the study of gelation as well as coagulation of ferric and aluminium phosphate sols effected by electrolytes at different temperatures. It has been also shown that $\log kpz = \alpha \log C + \beta$, where C is the concentration of the electrolyte, α and β are constants, and therefore $\log t = \alpha \log C + k_1$, where k_1 is constant provided E does not vary for different concentrations of the electrolyte. This relation of the time of coagulation and concentration of the coagulating electrolyte is very similar to those proposed by several other workers.

It is suggested here that p and E define the stability of the sol. E is large if (i) attractive force of the aggregating particle is small and (ii) the electric charge, which repel the particles to come together is large, whereas p increases with the decreasing electric charge on colloid particles effected by an electrolyte. It has been repeatedly observed that where E is large, kpz or p is also large, and such behaviour is so common for chemical reactions.

The sols of the phosphates of ferric and aluminium become unstable by adding dioxan, which lowers the dielectric constant of the medium and compresses the double layer, a behaviour similar to the initial condition produced by a coagulating electrolyte. But considerable lowering of energy of activation suggests that dioxan also increases the attractive force of the colloid particles of the two phosphate sols investigated here.

COLLOIDAL systems are thermodynamically unstable. The finely dispersed particles expose large surface area and therefore possess large free surface energy, which tends to decrease by their aggregation. The two recognised factors which check it are (i) electrical repulsion of the charged particles, and (ii) decrease of the free surface energy by such process as high solvation of colloid particles as in the case of lyophilic sols.

Action of electrolytes on lyophobic sols is to decrease the charge on the dispersed particles and thus render them unstable. Investigations from very early times led to such generalisations as Schulze-Hardy law and Whetham's rule for the precipitation values of different electrolytes. In a number of publications Ghosh and Dhar¹ showed that besides the valency of the oppositely charged ion, the specific adsorption of both similarly and oppositely charged ions, dilution of the sol, and even the mode of addition of the electrolyte (such as in parts or all at once) define its precipitation value. The phenomenon of positive acclimatization occurs because of the adsorption of similarly charged ions, whilst specific adsorption of the

oppositely charged ions leads to negative acclimatization, first reported by Ghosh and Dhar. Levine and Bell² also pointed out that variation in Schulze-Hardy law occurs due to specific adsorption of oppositely charged ions.

Whetham deduced that the precipitation values P_1, P_2, P_3 for mono-, bi-, and trivalent coagulating ions of an electrolyte bear a simple relation such that

$P_1 : P_2 : P_3 = 1 : x : x^2$, where x is less than unity. This relation is hardly found to be true.

Chakravarti, Ghosh and Dhar³ pointed out that the double layer surrounding the colloidal particle acts as a barrier for the approach of the oppositely charged ions to the colloid particle to neutralise its electric charge. Working on such assumption they modified Whetham's rule as

$P_1 : P_2 : P_3 = 1 : \frac{1}{2} \alpha : \frac{1}{3} \alpha^2 \dots \dots (i)$ and $\alpha = \exp\left(\frac{-Qe}{DrkT}\right)$, where Q is the charge on the colloid particle, e the electronic charge, D the dielectric constant, r the effective distance of the double layer, k the Boltzmann constant and T the

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absolute temperature. α is a proper fraction and tends to be unity when Q or the electric charge on the colloid particle is very small. In such a limiting case

$$P_1 : P_2 : P_3 = 1 : \frac{1}{3} : \frac{1}{3} \dots \dots (ii), \text{ later}$$

Verwey and Oberbeek⁴ considered the interaction of the double layers of two colliding charged dispersed units and have shown

$$P_1 : P_2 : P_3 = 1 : \left(\frac{1}{3}\right)^6 : \left(\frac{1}{3}\right)^6 \dots \dots (iii), \text{ when}$$

the colloidal particles are charged. The relation (ii) becomes

$$P_1 : P_2 : P_3 = 1 : \left(\frac{1}{3}\right)^2 : \left(\frac{1}{3}\right)^2 \dots \dots (iv), \text{ when}$$

the charge on the particles is removed.

Gore and Dhar⁵ dialysed a positively charged sol of ferric hydroxide to different extents and noted that as the purity of the sol is increased the precipitation values P_1, P_2, P_3 for chloride, sulphate and ferricyanide ions approach each other. Similar results were obtained by Ghosh and Rathi⁶ for ferric and aluminium phosphate sols, but they were unable to verify any of the relation (i) and (ii) or (iii) and (iv). It is necessary to state here that the relations have not taken into account the specific effect of the ions of the coagulating electrolytes on the dispersed particles, and therefore applicability of the equations derived by Dhar and Ghosh or Verwey and Overbeek cannot be expected to be true for different electrolytes.

Solvation and stability: High solvation of colloid particles as those of lyophilic sols renders them stable towards moderate concentrations of electrolytes. Most of the biocolloids such as gelatin, starch, belong to this group. However, there are a number of inorganic compounds, which yield viscous sols and their dispersed particles are highly solvated and easily yield gels by the action of electrolytes, and the gelation values for different electrolytes more or less follow Schulze-Hardy law⁷. Prakash and Dhar⁸ prepared gels of such inorganic compounds and studied their thixotropy and syneresis. It is suggested that such sols have highly solvated dispersed units but have some bare spots which join up on charge neutralisation entraining the solvent. The forces of binding are sufficiently loose so that the gel formed shows thixotropy and syneresis on ageing. Hauser⁹ made an ultramicroscopic study of the thixotropic behaviour of a highly solvated suspension of bentonite and observed that the suspended particles gradually lose Brownian movement and take up position though there is no material contact. Their movement can be easily revived by shaking. Banerji and Ghosh¹⁰ made rheological study of a viscous gel yielding sol of ferric phosphate and showed the plastic behaviour of the sol indicating the existence of a structure even in the so called fluid state. This shows that a loose structure is present in this sol.

Effect of non-electrolytes: The stability of sols towards an electrolyte has been largely investigated. Obviously a non-electrolyte cannot neutralise the charge on the colloid particles, but can well affect the electrical interactions of the charged particles

by varying the dielectric constant of the medium. If the lowering of dielectric constant decreases the thickness of the double layer, the effect is similar to that produced by the addition of an electrolyte to coagulate a sol. Freundlich¹¹ suggested that lowering of dielectric constant leads to decrease of the electric charge on the colloid particle and thus decreases the precipitation value of an electrolyte. Keesom¹² reported that the solutes, urea and glycol, increase the dielectric constant of water and render a sol of arsenious sulphide stable towards electrolytes. Mukherji, Raichoudhuri and Rao¹³ reported from the cataphoretic study of arsenious sulphide sol, that the mobility of colloid particles continuously decreases in an electrical field by the addition of a few non-electrolyte increasing or decreasing the dielectric constant of water. Prasad and Ghosh¹⁴ showed that glucose, which tends to decrease the dielectric constant, stabilises several hydroxide sols. Nand and Ghosh^{14a} observed that ferric hydroxide sol becomes unstable in the presence of dioxan, which remarkably lowers the dielectric constant of water. Yadav and Varma¹⁵ found that the sols of chromium and aluminium hydroxides become unstable in the presence of formamide, which increases the dielectric constant of water. It thus appears that factors other than the effect of the non-electrolyte on the dielectric constant are involved, which make a sol stable or unstable towards an electrolyte.

Equally a large amount of literature is available on the effect of non capillary and capillary active non-electrolytes on the stability of sols, but no general conclusion can be drawn from such results. Weiser¹⁶ therefore concluded that several factors describe the effect of a non-electrolyte on the stability of a sol. These are (i) dielectric constant of the medium, (ii) the viscosity, (iii) effect on ion activity and (iv) effect on the adsorption of ions of the coagulating electrolyte. It is necessary to mention here that a non-electrolyte effecting the free surface energy of the dispersed phase is also important for the stability of a sol.

Effect of time on precipitation value: Precipitation value of an electrolyte for a sol decreases with the increase in time of its contact with the sol. Several equations have been suggested from time to time to relate time of contact, 't', with the concentration of the electrolyte, C, added to coagulate the sol. Paine¹⁷ suggested the relation $-\log t = k_1 \log C + k_2$. (1) where k_1 and k_2 are constants and are similar to those of Mathews and Murphy¹⁸ viz., $1/t = aC^n$, where a and n are constants. von Smoluchowski¹⁹ considered that after the charge neutralisation of the colloid particles by an electrolyte, they combine when they are within the range of attraction, R, effected by diffusion process determined by the coefficient D so that,

$$\Sigma n = \frac{n_0}{1 + 4\pi DRn_0 t}, \text{ where } \Sigma n \text{ is the number of}$$

particles of all stages of aggregation left over after time 't' out of the total number of particles n_0 in the initial stage. It is assumed that DR remains

constant so that $4\pi DRn_0$ is constant and denoted by $\frac{1}{T}$. Smoluchowski further considered that during slow coagulation, the charge neutralisation on colloid particles is not complete and hence

$$\Sigma n = \frac{n_0}{1 + \epsilon \frac{t}{T}} \dots (2), \text{ where } \epsilon \text{ is less than unity.}$$

Ultramicroscopic investigations of Zsigmondy²⁰, and also of Westgren and Reitsstötter²¹ for the aggregation of particles of a gold sol by an electrolyte, and of Kruyt and van Arkel²² for that of a selenium sol show that the relation (2) is not applicable for ϵ continuously decreases and that the aggregation of coarser particles becomes so slow as if no further growth will occur.

Mukherji and Papaconstantino²³, and later Rai and Ghosh²⁴ and also Ghosh²⁵ used spectrophotometric method to study aggregation of colloid particles and showed that ϵ continuously decreases as the aggregation proceeds. Ghosh²⁶ pointed out that DR should progressively decrease as R cannot increase with the progress of aggregation as to compensate the decrease of D, so that DR remains constant. With increasing aggregation, the surface area and therefore surface energy per unit area continuously decreases.

Ghosh and coworkers²⁷ found that decrease of ϵ occurs with increasing time so that $\epsilon = \frac{k}{1 + \alpha t}$, where k and α are constants. Thus they modify the relation (2) as

$$\frac{\Sigma n}{n_0} = \frac{1 + at}{1 + bt} \dots (3), \text{ where } a \text{ and } b \text{ are constants and } b > a.$$

The above relation (3) is reported to be applicable for the coagulation of several sols, and thus proves the contention of Ghosh²⁶ that DR continuously decreases as R does not increase proportionately as more and more aggregated particles appear in the system.

It is well known that the time for complete coagulation decreases with increasing concentration of the coagulating electrolyte, and that beyond a certain concentration, the coagulation time t_r is more or less constant. This is the region of rapid coagulation and Reernik and Overbeek²⁸ defined the retarding or stability factor W as the ratio t_r/t_r , where t_r is the time for slow coagulation. Basing their calculations for the interacting particles with energy barrier arising out of the electric charge, they obtain the relation,

$$\log W = -k_1 \log C + k_2 \dots (4), \text{ where } k_1 \text{ and } k_2 \text{ are constants. Since } t_r \text{ is practically constant, equation (4) is similar to that of Paine. The plots of } \log W \text{ vs } \log C \text{ give a straight line, which gradually bends as } t_r \text{ approaches } t_r \text{ and finally runs parallel to } \log C \text{ axis, when } W \text{ becomes unity.}$$

An equation relating W with the concentration of the added electrolyte was proposed by Packter²⁹ viz.,

$$\log W = C_1 \gamma^4 - C_2 \gamma^2 \sqrt{C_e} \dots (5), \text{ where } C_1 \text{ and } C_2 \text{ are constants, } C_e \text{ is the concentration of electrolyte added, and } \gamma \text{ is defined by } \frac{\exp(Ze\Psi/2kt) - 1}{\exp(Ze\Psi/2kt) + 1}$$

where Z is the valency of the coagulating ion, e the electronic charge, Ψ the surface potential, k the Boltzmann constant and T the absolute temperature. The relation (5) is based on the theory of stability of sols and assumes that (i) for low concentration of the electrolyte only the double layer is compressed and (ii) that γ does not change when coagulation occurs.

Bhattacharya and Bhattacharya³⁰ proposed more or less an empirical relation $\frac{1}{c-a} = \frac{n}{m} t + \frac{1}{m} \dots (6)$,

where c is the concentration of the electrolyte added for coagulating the sol in time t , 'a' the concentration of the electrolyte coagulating the sol in infinite time and n and m are constants.

Ghosh³¹ deduced the above relation from the considerations of Verwey and Overbeek. The relation, however, is true for limited range of the concentration of the coagulating electrolyte³².

Effect of temperature on the stability of a sol: This was investigated by Lach and Goldbury³³, who found the time of coagulation, t , of a gold sol by an electrolyte proportional to η/T where η is the viscosity of the medium water. Similarly, Bose and Freundlich³⁴ found the applicability of a similar relationship for the slow coagulation of cupric oxide sol. Hurd and Latterson³⁵ investigated the effect of temperature for the gelation of silicic acid sol. Ghosh³⁶ also determined the effect of temperature of the same sol at different pH. Ghosh and co-workers³⁷ also studied the effect of temperature on the coagulation of some sols as well as the gelation of ferric succinate sol. All these investigations find that at higher temperature the sols become more unstable.

It is necessary to recall the concept of Reerink and Overbeek that coagulation is a bimolecular process specially in the initial stages,

$$\text{so that } -\frac{dn}{dt} = KN^2, \text{ where } N \text{ is the number of particles present initially, } n \text{ is the number of primary particles taking part in the aggregation process and } K \text{ is a constant, which varies with temperature i.e., } K = K_0 \exp\left(-\frac{E}{RT}\right),$$

where E is the energy of activation or the energy necessary to overcome the repulsive force due to electric charge. Verwey and Overbeek³⁸ related the stability factor W with the energy of activation as $\frac{1}{W} = \exp\left(-\frac{E}{RT}\right)$, so that when large concentration of an electrolyte is added, the coagulation becomes rapid where W is unity and therefore the heat of activation reduces to zero.

Ghosh³⁹ considers the aggregation process very similar to a chemical reaction as both the processes

occur through collision of particles. Aggregation of colloidal units first start with primary ones, and the newly formed unit can further grow by collision with primary or aggregated ones. This process continues till the aggregate becomes sufficiently large to lose its Brownian movement resulting in coagulation. Furthermore, the colliding particles first form an 'activated aggregate' by the collision of the two particles of requisite activation energy and the formation of the lasting aggregated units depends upon the probability factor p . If t is the time taken for complete coagulation of a definite amount of sol by the presence of an electrolyte and the rate taken as proportional to $\frac{1}{t}$, Ghosh and co-workers⁴⁰ suggest the relation

$$\frac{1}{t} = kpz \exp\left(-\frac{E}{RT}\right) \quad \dots (7)$$

$$\text{or } \log t = -\log kpz + \frac{E}{2.3RT} \quad \dots (8)$$

(a relation similar to a chemical process) where k is a constant, z the number of collision in unit time and T the absolute temperature. From the above relation it is seen that the stability of a sol depends on the values of p and Ghosh and co-workers⁴⁰ found the applicability of the relation (8) in as much as the plots of $\log t$ vs $\frac{1}{T}$ for a concentration of the coagulation electrolyte gave a straight line for the coagulation of some sols investigated by them earlier.

In this paper we have examined the applicability of the equation (8) for the gelation time for a ferric phosphate sol effected by an electrolyte at three stages of dialysis and also the sol of aluminium phosphate, which at its first and second stages of dialysis yields a bulky coagulum with an electrolyte but at its third stage gave a hazy gel.

Experimental

Ferric phosphate sol was prepared by the interaction of 1.0 l of 0.5 M FeCl_3 solution with 0.5 l of KH_2PO_4 . The sol so obtained was yellowish which on dialysis in a cellophane bag gradually became red. The analysis of the sol showed that gradually a basic iron phosphate or a mixture of $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_3$ and FePO_4 appeared with prolonged dialysis. These samples of the sols at different stages of dialysis were withdrawn and diluted with water so that the iron content of the three sols was the same i.e., 5.8 g of Fe per l. The three sols were designated as A_1, A_2

and A_3 and the pH of these were 2.7, 3.1 and 3.4, respectively. With further dialysis of the sol, the pH increased to 3.6 and formed a gel in the cellophane bag itself.

Aluminium phosphate sol was prepared by the interaction of 600 ml of 1.0 M aluminium chloride and 500 ml of 1.0 M of diammonium hydrogen phosphate solutions leaving some aluminium chloride in excess. The sol was diluted to 1500 ml and dialysed in a cellophane bag. Three samples of the sol were withdrawn at different stages of dialysis and diluted to contain 1.8 g of Al per l. The sols B_1, B_2 and B_3 were at pH 3.0, 3.4, 3.8 respectively. When coagulated by an electrolyte sols B_1 and B_2 yielded heavy coagula, whilst sol B_3 gave a hazy gel.

Method adopted to measure the gelation or coagulation time: Various optical methods are used to measure coagulation time of sols, but the formation of a transparent gel cannot be easily noted by any of them. There is hardly any change in the optical density when the sol sets to a gel, specially when the gelation process is slow. Hence gelation time is recorded by the observation that the gel formed does not flow out in a test tube of uniform diameter of 1.5 cm and 12.5 cm in length. The recorded time of gelation is the mean of three observations. In the case of coagulation of the sols B_1 and B_2 , the time was noted by the separation of the coagulum at the top layer in the test tube. It should be noted that the variation was within 2.5% when the time of observation was over 200 min, and it slightly decreased for smaller time. In Table 1, the observations for the gelation of sol A_1 by different concentrations of K_2SO_4 are recorded in the absence and also in the presence of the non-electrolyte dioxan, which decreases the dielectric constant of water remarkably and is sufficiently inert. The experiments have been carried out at four different temperatures in a thermostat.

To verify the applicability of relation (8) $\log t$ vs $\frac{1}{T}$ are plotted, and it will be seen that they yield straight lines for each concentration C of the electrolyte (see Fig. 1). From the inclination of the line the value of E can be obtained, and the value of $\log kpz$ can be calculated. These values of E and $\log kpz$ for different concentrations of electrolyte are given in Table 2. In a similar way the values of $\log kpz$ and E have been calculated when the gelation takes place in the presence of dioxan, and are also noted in Table 2.

As described above the values of E and $\log kpz$ have also been determined for the gelation of ferric

TABLE 1—GELATION OF FERRIC PHOSPHATE SOL A_1 BY POTASSIUM SULPHATE

Gelation value in m moles/litre $\times 10$	Time of gelation in min at				Time of gelation in min in 10% dioxan at			
	30°	35°	40°	45°	30°	35°	40°	45°
8.0	580	270	132	65.5	210	135	85	54.5
8.8	435	192	95	45	140	85	55	33.2
9.6	310	135	65.5	30.5	90.5	55	35.2	21.0
10.4	178	80	35	17.5	50	30.5	17.5	10.2
11.2	110	45	21	9.5	30.5	20.2	8.2	4.5
12.8	68	25	10.5	—	—	—	—	—
16.0	47	16	7	—	—	—	—	—

Fig. 1.

phosphate sols A_2 and A_3 , and also for the coagulation of aluminium phosphate sols B_1 and B_2 , as well as for the gelation of highly dialysed aluminium phosphate sol B_3 . All these values are given in Tables 3 to 7.

A perusal of Tables 2 to 7 shows that the values of $\log kpz$ and therefore p increase with the increasing concentrations of the electrolyte potassium sulphate, added for gelation or coagulation. It will be seen that the plots of $\log kpz$ vs $\log C$ yield straight lines (see Fig. 2) so that

$\log kpz = \alpha \log C + \beta \dots (9)$, where α and β are constants. Hence the relation (8) becomes

$\log t = -\alpha \log C - \beta + E/2.3 RT$, and if activation energy E does not vary, we have

$\log t = -\alpha \log C + k, \dots (10)$, which is very similar to those of Paine or Verwey and Overbeek relating the time of coagulation with the concentration of the coagulating electrolyte.

Ghosh and Roychowdhury⁴¹ have suggested

TABLE 2—GELATION OF FERRIC PHOSPHATE SOL A_1 BY POTASSIUM SULPHATE

log C × 10	0.9031	0.9445	Temperature range 30°–45°				
			0.9823	1.0170	1.0492	1.1072	1.2041
In aqueous medium							
log kpz	17.86	18.82	19.72	20.83	21.48	23.62	26.46
E in K cal	29.0	30.0	30.4	32.0	32.6	36.8	39.2
In 10% dioxan solution							
log kpz	10.85	11.46	12.05	12.72	16.27	—	—
E in K cal	18.4	19.0	19.6	20.2	24.8	—	—

TABLE 3—FERRIC PHOSPHATE SOL A_2 , ELECTROLYTE FOR GELATION : POTASSIUM SULPHATE

log C × 10	0.6812	0.7160	Temperature range 30°–45°					
			0.7482	0.7782	0.8062	0.8573	0.9031	0.9445
In aqueous medium								
log kpz	18.62	19.62	20.60	21.15	21.80	22.80	24.23	24.81
E in K cal	29.9	31.1	32.2	32.8	33.4	34.5	36.4	36.9
In 10% dioxan solution								
log kpz	12.57	13.14	13.77	14.42	—	—	—	—
E in K cal	20.7	21.3	21.9	22.5	—	—	—	—

TABLE 4—FERRIC PHOSPHATE SOL A_3 , ELECTROLYTE FOR GELATION : POTASSIUM SULPHATE

log C × 10	0.2041	0.2553	Temperature range 30°–45°					
			0.3010	0.3424	0.3802	0.4472	0.5315	0.6433
In aqueous medium								
log kpz	19.00	20.08	21.13	21.76	22.46	24.05	25.93	28.20
E in K cal	30.5	31.7	32.8	33.4	34.0	35.7	38.0	40.9
In 10% dioxan solution								
log kpz	13.82	14.89	15.56	16.27	—	—	—	—
E in K cal	22.5	23.6	24.2	24.8	—	—	—	—

TABLE 5—ALUMINIUM PHOSPHATE SOL B_1 , ELECTROLYTE FOR COAGULATION : POTASSIUM SULPHATE

log C × 10	2.2041	2.5553	Temperature range 30°–45°						
			2.3010	2.3424	2.3802	2.4150	2.4472	2.4771	2.5315
In aqueous medium									
log kpz	12.16	13.11	13.60	14.15	14.70	15.70	17.01	18.77	20.99
E in K cal	20.7	20.4	22.5	23.0	23.6	24.8	26.5	28.80	31.7
In 10% dioxan solution									
log kpz	7.95	8.91	9.89	11.25	12.07	14.05	15.84	17.25	—
E in K cal	14.4	15.5	16.7	18.4	20.7	21.9	24.2	25.9	—

TABLE 6—ALUMINIUM PHOSPHATE SOL B₂, ELECTROLYTE FOR COAGULATION : POTASSIUM SULPHATE

log C × 10	1.3424	1.380	Temperature range 36°–45°		1.5051	1.5315	1.5563	1.6021
			1.4150	1.4472	1.4771			
log kpz	14.34	15.24	In aqueous medium		18.45	19.01	20.78	22.67
E in K cal	23.4	24.5	16.18	17.12	28.6	29.1	31.4	32.4
			25.8	26.8				33.6
log kpz	9.10	9.62	In 10% dioxan solution		11.98	13.36	15.09	17.81
E in K cal	17.1	16.7	10.15	11.46	18.6	21.8	23.6	25.3
			17.3	18.0				27.1

TABLE 7—GELATION OF ALUMINIUM PHOSPHATE SOL B₃, ELECTROLYTE : POTASSIUM SULPHATE

log C × 10	0.4771	0.5441	Temperature range 36°–45°		0.7404	0.7782	0.8457	0.9031
			0.6021	0.6532	0.6990			
log kpz	15.66	16.61	In aqueous medium		21.13	23.71	25.08	27.01
E in K cal	25.90	27.1	17.96	19.77	32.8	36.3	38.0	40.0
			28.8	31.1				
log kpz	11.98	12.91	In 10% dioxan solution		17.38	19.96	22.58	—
E in K cal	19.6	20.7	15.09	15.64	26.5	29.9	33.4	—
			23.6	24.2				—

Fig. 2. Variation of log kpz with log C. Sol ferric phosphate and electrolyte potassium sulphate.

the following relation for t_s or time for slow coagulation :

$\log t_s = N(\epsilon + V_{max})/2.3 RT + B \dots (11)$, where ϵ is the activation energy related to the attraction of the molecules of water i.e. viscosity of the medium, V_{max} is the maximum in the potential energy curve for the two interacting colloidal units and B a constant. Obviously, relations (8) and (11) are similar for a particular concentration of the electrolyte and $N(\epsilon + V_{max})$ of equation (11) is identical to E of equation (8). It will be seen from our data presented here and also those obtained earlier by Ghosh and co-workers^{4,2} for several other sols that E continuously increases with increasing concentration of the electrolyte, but V_{max} should decrease because of the decreasing electric charge on colloid particles.

In Fig. 3, the effect of the rate of gelation or coagulation on the value of activation energy has been shown. It is seen that for slow coagulation the values of E slowly increase with the increasing rate and as the rate tends to become

rapid the activation energy also sharply increases. It appears that E is more related to the free surface energy than the electric charge on the dispersed particle or V_{max} of the potential energy curve. With larger concentrations of the electrolyte the charge on the colloid particles is more or less neutralised and primary and finer particles agglomerate rapidly yielding coarser ones of smaller surface energy for which higher activation energy is required for their further agglomeration.

From Fig. 3, the value of E_0 or the activation energy when the rate of coagulation or gelation is slowest for sol A₁ can be evaluated. Similarly, the values of E_0 for other sols A₂, A₃, B₁, B₂ and B₃ have been obtained. The values of E_0 for the sols investigated here are noted in Table 8, and it is found that for sols yielding gels the value of E_0 is more than 20 K cal, whilst for the sols B₁ and B₂, which produce bulky coagula, it is comparatively less. No doubt the gel yielding colloid particles are highly solvated and thus their surface energy is considerably moderated. For a truly lyophobic sol

Fig. 3. Sol. ferric phosphate ; electrolyte potassium sulphate : plot of E vs $1/T$ (Temperature 35°).

as that of silver the value of E_0 has been found to be 8 K cal⁴⁸.

TABLE 8

Sol	A ₁	A ₂	A ₃	B ₁	B ₂	B ₃
E_0 (K cal)	25.0	27.0	27.5	16	20	21
Nature of the coagulum	gel	gel	gel	bulky coagulum	very bulky coagulum	hazy gel

Addition of dioxan to the sols investigated here considerably affects the precipitation or gelation values for an electrolyte, i.e. the sols become unstable. Dioxan lowers the dielectric constant of water. Obviously this lowering of the dielectric constant compresses the double layer of the charged particles and these may now approach nearer and come within their attractive range. Such condition is also created when an electrolyte is added to a sol. Our experimental data show that as more and more of an electrolyte is added to a sol the activation energy tends to increase and as the coagulation or gelation becomes rapid it sharply increases. It is interesting to find that dioxan increases the rate of gelation or coagulation effected by a definite concentration of the electrolyte, but the activation energy is remarkably decreased. This suggests that the lowering of dielectric constant increases the free surface energy of the colloid particles composed of the phosphates of iron or aluminium. Ghosh and Sengupta⁴⁴ studied the effect of dioxan on negatively charged sulphur sols (prepared by two different methods) and reported that these sols become very sensitive to electrolytes in the presence of dioxan, but the activation energy increased considerably.

A perusal of Table 1 will show that the rate of gelation of ferric phosphate by an electrolyte becomes about four times or more for 10° rise in temperature. This itself suggests that an "activated aggregate" is first formed by the collision of colloidal particles of sufficient energy (activation

energy) and that such an "activated aggregate" yields a stable aggregated particle depending upon the probability factor p . The stability of a lyophobic sol towards an electrolyte therefore depends upon the values of E and p .

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